

CHANGES IN THE WORLD'S ECOLOGICAL PARADIGM

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Annotation: This article analyzes the harmonious development of the relationship between humans and nature, as well as how their interaction impacts the changing ecological landscape of the world and affects the current global ecological balance. It explores the role of humanity in maintaining environmental equilibrium, focusing on human activities related to living, production, consumption, and management. In addition, the article presents scientific and theoretical conceptual ideas aimed at creating a sustainable ecological environment.

Key words: ecology, environment, biosphere, climate, ecological culture, paleography, historical geology, geochemistry, paleontology, society.

Throughout the course of human development, alongside the growth of intellectual potential, material needs have also increased. As activities aimed at satisfying these needs exceeded rational limits, humanity's relationship with the surrounding environment and the world began to change – more specifically, it led to a growing alienation from nature. “Alienation is a social process in which human activity and its outcomes take on an independent force, becoming dominant over the individual and acting against them. It manifests in the absence of social control over the conditions, means, and products of labor, as well as in the transformation of the individual into an object of manipulation by dominant social groups through deceptive means”. Alienation is reflected in a person's

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consciousness in a specific way (such as perceiving social norms as foreign and hostile, feelings of loneliness, indifference, etc.). The origins of the concept of alienation can be traced back to T. Hobbes and J. J. Rousseau, and it was later developed by Hegel. In the 20th century, certain aspects of alienation have been studied in philosophy, sociology, and social psychology [1]. In the Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary, it is interpreted as “a disruption of the primordial connection between a person and their place, status, and role in society” [2]. The disruption of norms in the relationship between the individual and society – where a person is deprived of the qualities that define their essence and is unable to find their place in society – constitutes the root of alienation, serving as both its cause and consequence. Western sociologists regard various phenomena as manifestations of alienation: the loss of a sense of solidarity in industrial society (Durkheim), the formalization of social life (Simmel), the deviation of individual behavior from social norms (Merton), and the capacity to develop a critical attitude toward the existing society (Fromm). In contemporary Western society, alienation has become so widespread that it has taken on the character of a social phenomenon. American psychologist M. Maccoby even identifies a specific type of person – “the warrior in the jungle” – who is alienated from all others in society and sees them as enemies. It is emphasized that alienation, as a concept, requires further research and analysis [2]. Professor V. Alimasov also defines the phenomenon of alienation as “a socio-philosophical concept that signifies a person’s estrangement from society, from governance, and from the relationships and objectified things they themselves have created” [3].

Alienation can be defined as the opposition of humans to nature, the intensification of the belief in the superiority of the human “self” over all other living beings in the biosphere, and, simultaneously, the loss of human dignity. This idea is reflected in events such as the “European Year of Nature Conservation” (1970), the UN Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm (1972),

as well as in articles published by Western scholars such as Jay Forrester, Donella and Dennis Meadows commissioned by the Club of Rome. In particular, their articles on the topic “The Limits to Growth” (1971-1972) focus special attention on this very issue. The violation of the natural value of the human-nature relationship should be understood as the alienation of humans from nature, or the transformation – within human consciousness – of the natural connections between people and the environment (both external to and within the individual) into something perceived as nonexistent.

Although the technological advancements of the 21st century have created improved living conditions for humanity, on the other hand, humanity has also encountered problems in this era that it cannot solve alone. Such problems are not specific to a single country or nation but affect the entire planet. Therefore, such globally significant issues have always been the focus of attention for national governments and international organizations, and concrete measures are being taken to address them. The development of industry and population growth have led to the emergence of new problems in the field of ecology. On this issue, the preface to the Russian edition of renowned scholar Peter Farb’s book “Ecology for Beginners” emphasizes the following: “With each passing year, the importance of ecology continues to grow. Indeed, under no circumstances will humanity abandon efforts to solve ecological problems, because failing to address such issues could pose a threat to human life”. According to experts in the field, “In the 21st century, ecology will become one of the highest priorities in the global system of international relations”. For example, nearly half a century ago, academician A. Pokrovskiy wrote: “Modern humans have always been in a state of war with nature. The destructive consequences of this are becoming increasingly evident year by year. If we do not cultivate an ecological culture in humanity’s relationship with nature, it could lead to tragic consequences” [4].

Providing our planet with clean water is currently one of the most pressing global issues attracting the attention of the international community. Regarding this global situation, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: “Analytical calculations show that by 2040, the demand for water resources in some Central Asian countries will triple. Over time, the economic damage caused by water scarcity could reach up to 11 percent of the gross domestic product”. According to UN data, countries in the region are already losing up to 2 billion US dollars annually due to water resource scarcity and inefficient use [5]. Despite many countries around the world possessing underground resources such as oil and gas, they still suffer from a shortage of clean drinking water. As a result, attention to water-related issues is increasing day by day, and solving this problem has become a central topic of regional and international conferences. Such forecasts indicate that solving the water problem is not limited to a single country or region – it is a matter of global concern. In other words, in the 21st century, the globalization of environmental issues such as water scarcity and climate change has turned them into key factors shaping international relations. These issues can be examined at the levels of bilateral relations between individual states, as well as at regional and international levels. The problem of clean water scarcity, its purification and efficient use, as well as the prevention of water-related risks, has compelled the Republic of Uzbekistan to take the initiative in addressing these issues. For this reason, special attention has been given in our state policy to “eliminating existing environmental problems that harm public health and the gene pool” [6].

The global ecological mission is not limited to studying the impact of human activity on the biosphere and its components – atmosphere, hydrosphere, and lithosphere – or the changes in their chemical composition, physical and biological properties. It also involves exploring the laws governing the development of nature itself. It was clear to Vernadsky that under the influence of rational human activity, the biosphere would transition to a qualitatively new state. He called this new,

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transformed state of the biosphere – reshaped by human thought and labor – the noosphere. Its key characteristic is the maintenance of global system balance based on the optimal harmony between socio-historical and natural laws [7].

To study the state of the biosphere, data from meteorological and climate stations, oceanography, Earth’s artificial satellites, remote sensing materials, as well as sources from paleography, historical geology, geochemistry and paleontology, geophysics, field observations, and other related fields are used. There are many global environmental problems; nevertheless, every informed citizen of any country, at the very least, holds an opinion on environmental issues and their impact on Uzbekistan’s climate, hydroenergy, geographic, hydrological, landscape, geophysical, and geochemical conditions.

Today, global ecological factors are not limited to studying the impact of human activity on the biosphere and its components – namely the atmosphere, hydrosphere, and lithosphere – or the changes in their physical, chemical, and biological properties. They also encompass the study of the laws governing the ongoing development of nature.

The concept of alienation is a social process that describes how human activity and its outcomes become an independent force, gaining dominance over the individual and acting against them.

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